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Research on Development of Sports Culture at Universities in the Digital Age

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ABSTRACT

In the digital age, the Internet has evolved into a close-knit data space, with fast-developing technologies like big data algorithms and social media platforms changing our way of life and sports culture at universities. Thanks to big data algorithms, universities and sports administrations can identify the students' preferences and needs for sports more accurately, thereby realizing better management of physical education and evaluation of sports culture. Against this backdrop, sports administrations in universities need to consider how to boost development of sports culture on campus in light of the features of physical exercises of college students. The present study also analyzed the problems in physical education in universities and proposed recommendations in an attempt to provide a basis for development of sports culture at universities.

Introduction

On 10th January 2019, the Ministry of Industry of Information Technology of China issued temporary 5G plates, which kickstarted the commercialization of 5G technology. With the advent of the 5G age, offline life goes online, which turbocharges social changes and progress [1], leaving tremendous impacts on social culture and people's daily life. College students, with keen perception to cultural elements, are fashion trail-blazers. Then, what the sports administration staff in universities can do to seize on the opportunities brought about by digitalization to promote development sports culture in universities as per the features of physical exercises of college students? This study aims to find answers to this question.

Digitalization plays a contributing role to integration of in-school physical education and off-school physical exercises

Integration of in-school physical education and off-school physical exercise means combining in-school physical education (PE) classes and off-school physical exercises to motivate the students to take in knowledge of sports, increase their frequency of physical exercises at school, and improve their physical health. Thanks to digital technology, PE classes can be delivered both online and offline. In particular, with the help of mobile apps and applets, PE classes extend beyond the school and thus combination of in-school physical education with off-school physical exercise is achieved. With more and more access to physical exercise data of students out of school, universities can mine from these data the students' needs for physical education accurately to provide customized services and engage students in physical exercises. In this way, more students will take part in extracurricular physical exercises and students are more likely to develop a life-long habit of keeping fit. Investigations on extracurricular physical exercises among freshmen and sophomores at universities revealed that over 50% of the investigated students considered extracurricular physical exercises important (Table 1), and 68.71% took exercises three times a week (Table 2).

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Table 1. Recognition of importance of extracurricular exercise among college students

Indicator	Very important	A little important	Important	Not very important	Not important at all
Number of persons	261	158	51	19	0
Percentage	53.37%	32.31%	10.43%	3.89%	0

Table 2. Times of 30-min physical exercise every week among the students

Indicator	≥ 4	3	2	1	< 1
Number of persons	82	254	109	35	9
Percentage	16.77%	51.94%	22.29%	7.16%	1.84%

Features of sports culture in the digital age

Win-win cooperation between fashion and sports

Thanks to the popularity of digital marketing channels, sports stars go beyond the realm of sports and are embraced by fashion brands because of their sunning, positive and healthy images. The sportsmanship featured by optimism and never-give-up spirit becomes the major culture that sports stars introduce to fashion brands. As the statistics of Forbes show, Tiger Woods who topped the list of the wealthiest athletes in 2013 earned up to 65 million US dollars from endorsements for brands. Other sports stars like Kobe Bryant, Roger Federer and David Beckham have had close connections with Nike, Rolex, Armani and other fashion brands. Li Na, another household name who had already endorsed brands like Nike, Rolex and Haagen-Dazs, was invited for endorsement for Mercedes-Benz after her claim to the Grand Slam championship.

The win-win collaboration between the fashion industry and the sports sector has become an inevitable trend. Examples in this regard abound: the sportswear jointly designed by Stella McCartney and Adidas introduced the aesthetics of fashion to sports; the sports collection that Ralph Lauren, a famous fashion brand in America, sponsored the Team USA with in the Olympics increased the brand's popularity; large sports events are occasions celebrated both by the sports and the fashion sectors. Sports events organizers need support, in both manpower and material, from sponsors; and for fashion brands, sponsoring sports events will allow them to reach a larger base of customers and improve the brand images. Win-win collaborations between these two sectors are countless — cooperation between Wimbledon Championship and Rolex, between Formula One, Golf matches and Omega, Gucci's sponsorship of the Grand Steeple-Chase de Paris in 2009, IWC's sponsorship of Volvo Ocean Race in 2011; in the World Cup 2011, the FIFA World Cup was presented in a tailor-made box of Louis Vuitton. Collaboration in different aspects between sports and fashion increases the value of both and reaches a win-win result. "Fashion is a big net into which the sports have been deeply woven" [2].

Aristocratic sports as a way of creational fashion

In the West, engagement in aristocratic sports is considered a lifestyle worth leading and an upbeat attitude towards life: to strive for achievements and a better life while boosting social progress. This attitude will also affect others and allow others to learn the importance of hard work. In this logic, there will be a virtuous cycle. Thus, aristocratic sports are considered a manifestation of fashion [3]. As the middle- and high-income class rises in China, the aristocratic sports have shifted from a symbol of power, wealth and social connections to pursuit of happiness and a better life with dignity. Because of this pursuit, the Chinese people have kept in line with the world in terms of the quality of life and the taste for fashion.

Tennis, an aristocratic game, used to be a gentle form of entertainment among aristocrats in the Europe. As China's women's tennis broke records one after another in the global arena, a wave of popularity of tennis was sparked across the nation. Meanwhile, golf has turned from a dream to a reality for more and more people in China [4]. Polo used to be a lavish game among the gentlefolk in the West, but statistics show that there are up to 500 riding clubs of scale in China, with over 100 in Beijing and an increasing number of clubs in second- and third-tier cities. Partial surveys show that there are more than 300,000 fans of horse riding across China, with a growth rate rising year by year [5].

Sports as a fashionable lifestyle pursued by college students

Fashion leaders are principally renowned public figures with high social standing. Every aspect of life of the

celebrities and stars — what they wear and eat, where they live and how they travel — become a form of fashion that the fans follow. Sometimes, a casual move or gesture of a celebrity or star becomes a new vogue among the fans [6]. Physical fitness and never-give-up sportsmanship are the most valuable cultural outputs of the sports celebrities. Household names of sports stars like Woods, Federer and Jordon have already lifted their specific field of sports to unprecedented popularity. In sports commercials, these sports stars are morphed into super stars on par with movie stars. In the commercials, the golf players can hit the ball to wherever the player wants it to be or even make a hole-in-one; basketball players make spectacular slam dunks one after another without a cinch; football athletes can score goals with anything round-shaped. After breaking records one after another, these athletes are deified as superheroes who break rules on the earth [7]. The brands they endorse are undoubtedly considered the best of a kind. Because of the college students' high sensitivity and quick response to fashion, these sports stars' moves are mimicked in an exponential manner and evolve into a lifestyle.

Impacts of digitalization on sports in universities

Increasing the vigor of sports in universities

Fashion culture enriches the meaning and form of sports in universities. Under the impact of fashion culture, more fashionable sports activities rise among the college students, such as billiards, tennis, archery, free fighting, Latin dancing, camping, rock-climbing, yoga, bowling, taekwondo, golf, boxing, scuba diving, drifting and surfing, and some fit-keeping sports (aerobics, gymnastics, figure training, Pilates), beach volleyball, soft volleyball, cheerleading, sports dancing, and street dancing. In this context, the General Administration of Sport of China provided the following definition for fashion sports: fashion sports are social sport activities that have risen to popularity among the people, benefiting people's physical, mental, intellectual wellbeing, and serving socializing and recreational purposes [8]. It is not hard to see that popularity of these sports at universities has enriched the content of sports activities in universities.

Quick rise to popularity and fast decline to oblivion is an inherent feature of fashion and manifests the short life cycle of fashion culture. Fashion sports, as a new form of social culture, rises and spreads with notable features — it changes, develops and updates with the times, which increases the standards for professionalism of PE teachers and management skills of sports administrations in universities. If the standards are not met, the vigor of physical education at universities will suffer. Therefore, the teachers should update their knowledge network to keep up with the times and thus adapt to the reforms of physical education at universities. Only by improving themselves can the teachers keep up with the times and meet the needs of physical education, maintain the vitality of sports activities at universities, and reach the goals of all-round development.

Undermining the development of traditional sports culture

Traditional sports culture of China has been sidelined by fashion sports culture. The modern fashion culture, which is innovative, avant-garde and anti-traditional, finds it easy to win favor from college students. Traditional sports culture, however, begins to lose favor and is under the crisis of falling into oblivion at universities. To reverse the situation, universities should save the traditional sports culture from extinction through reforms of physical education [9]. This, in fact, is an irreversible trend. Traditional sports culture should keep up with the times, because as the time proceeds, people's preferences for sports vary, and to survive and develop in the modern world, traditional sports culture should learn from the fashion sports culture, and make innovations in response to the challenges. Universities should sort out traditional and modern features of traditional sports culture, develop the traditional sports culture to keep up with the times. Only by meeting the needs of the times can a culture survive and gain development.

Recommendations

Improving digital management of physical education and assuming a responsible role in leading a trend of sports in society

College students are a pool of talents for universities and the society, and play a crucial role in social development and progress of civilization, so they must assume a responsible role in inheritance and development of culture. Universities and sports administration departments, with the help of advanced technologies like big data algorithms, can accurately identify the preferences and needs of students for sports, and thereby realize precise delivery of messages of sports administration and accurate evaluation of the effect of creating sports culture. Against this backdrop, sports administration departments at universities should consider how to make use of the features of sports among college students to boost the development of sports culture in universities in the digital age. The very reason why the fashion culture in universities survives and gains momentum is that it emphasizes understanding and reflection, encourages inclusiveness and inspiration, and seeks to make breakthroughs through experiments. This culture helps train the college students' awareness and

skills of innovation, and is in line with the educational goals of universities to train innovative talents. College students who are fond of fashionable elements will generate new fashion trends by combining different elements of fashion. Sports administration departments at universities should promote positive, healthy and fashionable sports culture, encourage innovation of sport activities on campus, create classical forms of sports, and play a leading role in promoting physical exercise and sports in the society.

Inheriting traditional sports culture and making innovations

The traditional sports culture is overshadowed by the fashion sports culture in the modern world because the former has lost appeal to the students, which is worthy of reflection by the sports administration staff. When inheriting traditional sports culture and making innovations, universities should adopt diverse promotion channels to retain the core of traditional sports culture while drawing on excellent elements from fashion sports culture. In this way, the content of traditional sports culture can be enriched, with both traditional and modern appeal to win favor with students. Besides, Chinese universities can research and learn experiences from the development of traditional sports abroad, such as taekwondo from South Korea and yoga from India, to protect traditional sports from unfavorable impacts and fit the traditional sports culture into the modern world. All fashion sports are spread and promoted after packaging, and from the perspective of promotion, fashion sports are not only games, but a lifestyle and a taste for fashion. Thus, packaging and promotion should be a key part in inheriting traditional sports culture and making innovations.

Conclusion

Sports have become a modern lifestyle of fashion, and the rise and boom of numerous sports apps and applets provide a glimpse into the society's attitude towards sports. Sports culture in universities reflects the characteristics of the times, and it has been a constant state of change, development and upgrading. Universities should be inclusive to different forms of fashion culture, embrace digital management, and develop healthy and fashionable sports culture. Meanwhile, it is advisable to inherit traditional sports culture and make innovations to fit the traditional sports into the modern world. Also, sports administration departments in universities should probe into the characteristics of modern fashion sports culture and play a leading role in promoting sports culture in the society. This is the orientation for reforms of sports education in universities and is beneficial for development of sports culture in universities and the society.

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